

A Scanning Microwave Microscopy Study of FIB-Induced Impedance Changes in InGaAs/InP and HfO₂/InGaAs/InP Heterostructures

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ABSTRACT

Focused ion beam (FIB) milling is a powerful direct-write approach for nanoscale structuring of semiconductor heterostructures, but it inevitably induces structural, compositional, and electrical modifications that require complementary characterization techniques for proper assessment. In this work, scanning microwave microscopy (SMM) is used as the primary probe to follow the evolution of the local impedance response induced by Ga⁺ FIB milling in two III-V-based stacks relevant to mid-infrared photonics: an uncapped 150 nm heavily doped InGaAs layer on InP and a HfO₂ (35 nm)/InGaAs (150 nm)/InP heterostructure. By combining SMM with atomic force microscopy (AFM) and Raman spectroscopy, the study correlates changes in amplitude and phase of the microwave reflection coefficient S₁₁ with implantation, amorphization, oxide degradation, roughening, and the progressive exposure of the underlying semiconductor layers. The uncapped InGaAs/InP sample shows a relatively direct evolution of the SMM signal with dose, consistent with progressive Ga implantation and the transition from InGaAs-dominated to InP-dominated response. In the HfO₂-capped structure, the microwave response is more complex: the oxide initially acts as a partial buffer, delaying damage transfer to the semiconductor, but its protective effect diminishes at higher doses, leading to a mixed response associated with degradation, semiconductor damage, and multilayer coexistence within the irradiated regions. Raman spectra support these trends by revealing dose-dependent broadening and intensity changes in the vibrational bands, while AFM confirms the onset of roughening and morphological inhomogeneity at high doses. Overall, the results show that SMM is highly sensitive to nanoscale electrical and dielectric gradients generated by FIB milling and provides subsurface information that cannot be captured by morphology alone, making it a valuable tool for the optimization of FIB processing in plasmonic III-V heterostructures, owing to its high sensitivity in detecting implantation at very low doses.

1. Introduction

Heavily n-doped semiconductors, including InGaAs, have attracted significant interest for mid-infrared (mid-IR) plasmonic and photonic applications because their high free-carrier density enables strong plasmonic nonlinearities and relatively low-loss waveguiding in compact all-semiconductor integrated platforms [1-3]. These properties make InGaAs-based heterostructures on InP substrates promising candidates for on-chip mid-IR sources, modulators, and detectors, especially when integrated with metal gates and high-k dielectrics such as HfO₂ [4], to exploit electro-optic effects through electrostatic modulation of the carrier density in the InGaAs layer [5].

In addition to resist-based lithography approaches for device fabrication, maskless and direct-write micro/nano-fabrication techniques such as focused ion beam (FIB) milling [6] are particularly attractive for the rapid prototyping of novel photonic devices with nanoscale precision and may represent a powerful route for structuring complex III-V heterostructures, including InGaAs-based stacks. However, FIB milling with Ga⁺ ions inevitably induces structural damage, including amorphization, Ga implantation, and selective sputtering, even at relatively low doses because of beam-tail effects [7-10]. Previous studies on III-V

semiconductors have documented amorphized sidewall layers in InP, InAs, and GaAs, with thicknesses exceeding those predicted by simple implantation models owing to dynamic damage accumulation [11]. In InP, recoil-induced phosphorus disorder introduces additional defects, whereas GaAs generally does not exhibit recrystallized phases under comparable conditions [10].

In heavily doped InGaAsP quantum wells and InP-based structures, FIB milling has also been associated with Ga segregation, metallic cluster formation [12-14], while increased optical losses arising from implantation and local heating have been evidenced in GaAs [15]. More generally, high-energy ion irradiation can generate deep levels that alter material properties, including reduced carrier mobility [16], as well as changes in dielectric constant variations from defect-induced permittivity changes [17]. Notably, few reports address heavily doped InGaAs or HfO₂-capped variants on InP, leaving a gap in understanding nanoscale electrical/dielectric gradients critical for plasmonic performance.

Therefore, focused ion beam treatment is expected to alter the local electrical and dielectric properties over shallow and intermediate depths, which are highly relevant for the operation of plasmonic heterostructures. Scanning microwave microscopy (SMM) is particularly suitable for probing such modifications because it is a non-destructive scanning probe technique that provides nanoscale access to the local complex impedance of the material through the microwave reflection coefficient S₁₁ [18-20]. SMM is sensitive to both capacitive and resistive contributions and can be used to map local variations in conductivity, permittivity, and carrier density with sub-surface sensitivity [21,22]. In contrast to conventional conductive atomic force microscopy (AFM), which is mainly sensitive to tip-sample contact resistance, SMM probes a significantly larger interaction volume and is therefore well suited to the investigation of buried interfaces, dielectric overlayers, and multilayer semiconductor stacks.

Quantitative and semi-quantitative approaches based on calibration and de-embedding of S₁₁ have further enabled the extraction of capacitance, resistance, resistivity, and dopant concentration in semiconductor systems [23-25]. To date, these approaches have been most successful on relatively simple model systems, such as single-semiconductor samples with known implanted dopants [24] or dielectric stacks with well-defined capacitor geometries [26, 27]. By contrast, the quantitative characterization of electrical properties in complex multilayer structures remains largely unexplored and will require more robust and accurate evaluation strategies to enable the extraction of reliable material parameters. Nevertheless, SMM remains highly relevant for the qualitative characterization of FIB-milled semiconductor heterostructures, including the InGaAs/InP-based systems investigated here, where implantation, amorphization, and compositional changes are expected to generate nanoscale gradients in electrical and dielectric response that cannot be captured by an approach relying solely on a combination of morphological and spectroscopic characterization.

Scanning microwave microscopy is employed here to investigate the electrical response at the microwave due to local impedance variations in III-V materials subjected to Ga⁺ FIB milling, with and without an HfO₂ dielectric top layer. By combining SMM with AFM-based morphological analysis and Raman spectroscopy, the effects induced by 30 kV Ga⁺ irradiation in n⁺-InGaAs (150 nm)/InP and HfO₂ (35 nm)/n⁺-InGaAs (150 nm)/InP heterostructures are characterized over a wide dose range, from very low doses to high milling regimes. The results reveal distinct damage mechanisms and responses, including implantation, amorphization, and roughening, which must be carefully considered when optimizing FIB processing of mid-IR plasmonic nanodevices. They also show that SMM is highly sensitive to early-stage FIB-induced modifications, even when the topographic changes are still minimal.

2. Experimental section

2.1 Sample preparation

Samples were grown by metalorganic vapor phase epitaxy (MOVPE) on InP in a Veeco D180 Turbodisc reactor: (i) 150 nm thick n⁺ doped InGaAs ($n = 8.8 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$); (ii) 35 nm HfO₂ grown by atomic layer deposition (ALD) on 150 nm n⁺ doped InGaAs. A FEI Helios Nanolab 600 dual-beam FIB equipped with a Ga⁺ metal ion source (was used for FIB patterning at 30 keV, with beam current ranging from 1pA to 24 pA under normal incidence. Arrays of 3x3 μm^2 and 4x4 μm^2 areas were milled on the sample surfaces. On InGaAs/InP a FIB dose in the $2.0 \times 10^{14} - 8.2 \times 10^{16} \text{ ions/cm}^2$ range was employed to treat with ions 25 square areas. For the HfO₂/InGaAs/InP sample, two arrays of 25 square FIB milled areas were patterned using two

different intervals of ion doses: i) in a first set the same interval as for the case of InGaAs/InP sample was used (2.0×10^{14} - 6.1×10^{16} ions/cm²); ii) a second array of 25 areas was milled using a larger ion dose interval (5.6×10^{12} - 3.1×10^{17} ions/cm²). The two intervals have overlap and several ion doses are matching. The upper range of the second range was selected to obtain areas where FIB milling proceeded into the InP layer for at least several hundred nanometers. The electron column of the FIB system was used for SEM imaging.

2.2 Atomic force microscopy - Scanning microwave microscopy

AFM morphology measurements were made both in dynamic mode (force constant of ~ 40 N/m, resonant frequency ~ 300 kHz) using silicon probes with 5 nm curvature radius. Profiles and depth measurements of the milled areas were obtained by averaging over at least 10 lines in the FIB treated areas.

SMM measurements were performed using a Nanosurf Flex AFM equipped with a Nanosurf SMM module operating at around 5.7 GHz. SMM probes have Pt/Ir bulk cantilevers (Rocky Mountain Nanotechnology, RMN 25PtIr300B, resonant frequency of ~ 19 kHz, force constant ~ 22 N/m), employed in contact mode with set-point force of ~ 20 nN and scan rate 0.5 Hz (pixel resolution 256×256 and 512×512 , scan area from $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$ to $35 \times 35 \mu\text{m}^2$). Local complex reflection coefficient S11 amplitude and phase data maps were collected using Nanosurf SMM module coupled with the AFM.

2.3 Micro-Raman spectroscopy

Micro-Raman spectra in each FIB milled area were collected in back-scattering geometry by using a DXR2xi Thermo Fisher Raman Imaging Microscope. The measurements were performed by exciting the samples at 532 nm with 5 mW laser power and a $50\times$ objective. Each spectrum resulted from 1000 accumulations of 200 ms acquisitions. The spectra have been compared after smoothing (Savitzky-Golay filter with a 5-point window), fluorescence background subtraction (polynomial of order 3), and baseline correction.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Morphological analysis - SEM and AFM morphology of FIB milled areas

The morphology of the samples was analyzed using SEM and AFM. In the InGaAs/InP sample, the FIB-treated areas exhibit a generally smooth and uniform surface (Fig. 1a-c). The ion dose range investigated allowed to produce square pits in the InGaAs film at the lower doses, and to remove the entire InGaAs and 150 nm of the InP bottom substrate at the highest ion dose. At intermediate doses (1×10^{16} - 5×10^{16} ions/cm²), the typical formation of metallic gallium droplets is observed, commonly detected on GaAs-based materials irradiated with FIB [12]. The Ga droplets tend to coalesce and then progressively decrease in volume and number, until they disappear upon complete consumption of the InGaAs film. The FIB milling rate on InGaAs and InP is very similar, as evidenced by the nearly linear milling depth versus ion dose curve shown in Fig. 1d. A slight decrease in milling rate is observed around the ion doses close to the transition between the two materials, likely due to presence of the interface between the two materials. AFM measurements showed an increase in the sample volume in the irradiated areas at the lowest ion dose of around 2×10^{14} - 3×10^{14} ions/cm², corresponding to a mound ~ 0.6 - 0.7 nm thick. Such swelling behavior at this very low dose regime points to a marked incorporation (implantation) of gallium into the InGaAs when the milling mechanism is not yet fully active, while at slightly higher doses of $\sim 5 \times 10^{14}$ ions/cm² and larger, milling effect is well detectable.

It is worth noting that after few AFM scans in contact mode, even at low force as low as 20 nN, almost all the Ga droplets are moved aside the scan area leaving a smooth semiconductor surface, as visible in the AFM maps of Fig. 1b, c. The surface roughness (R_s) of the FIB milled area was measured after few preliminary scans showing values below 1 nm for ion doses below 4×10^{16} ions/cm² and between 1 nm and 2 nm for doses in the 4×10^{16} - 8×10^{16} ions/cm² range.

FIGURE 1. Morphology of the InGaAs/InP sample treated by FIB at increasing ion dose on a 5x5 matrix of 3 μm wide square areas. (a) SEM micrograph. (b) 3D view of AFM topography. (c) 2D AFM map (a section profile of the upper second row of FIB-treated areas is superimposed on the topography map). (d) Depth of the FIB-treated areas as measured with AFM.

FIB milling on the $\text{HfO}_2/\text{InGaAs}/\text{InP}$ sample was performed by irradiating with gallium ions two 5x5 arrays of square areas (3 μm size) at increasing doses in the two ranges described in Section 2.1. The SEM and AFM topography images relative to the array in the dose range 2.0×10^{14} - 6.1×10^{16} ions/ cm^2 are shown in Figure 2a, c, e. The SEM and AFM topography images corresponding to the second treatment range (5.6×10^{12} - 3.1×10^{17} ions/ cm^2) are shown in Figure 2b, limited to the ten highest doses used. The milling depth measured in the two sets of treated areas is reported in the graph in Fig. 2f.

A pronounced morphological variation is evident at FIB doses corresponding to the milling transition from the HfO_2 film to the underlying InGaAs film, around a dose of approximately 8.9×10^{16} ions/ cm^2 . In this transient region, the surface morphology changes from smooth with well-defined profiles for milling depths below 35 nm (corresponding to the HfO_2 film thickness) to a highly rough character. This occurs due to the inhomogeneity in the removal of the last HfO_2 layer, where voids are formed non-uniformly. Due to the marked difference in milling rate between HfO_2 and InGaAs (the ratio of the HfO_2 milling rate relative to the two III-V materials is approximately 1:12), at these voids the underlying InGaAs is milled rapidly. This morphological inhomogeneity persists at increasing doses, even after the hafnium oxide film is removed, and leads to a less regular transition between the layers, favoring the coexistence of the HfO_2 and InGaAs films, and even of the underlying InP film, within the same patch at the highest set of ion doses (8×10^{16} - 3×10^{17} ions/ cm^2). It is worth noting that small pillars of HfO_2 are still visible at an ion dose as high as 1.3×10^{17} ions/ cm^2 where the surrounding materials have been milled to a depth of approximately 150nm. This rough pattern is visible for the five highest doses of the first square array of treated areas (Fig. 2a, c, e) and for the seven highest doses of the ten areas shown in Figure 2b, d.

FIGURE 2. Morphology of the $\text{HfO}_2/\text{InGaAs}/\text{InP}$ sample treated by FIB. (a, b) SEM micrographs of area treated with two different dose ranges: (a) (1.9×10^{14} - 6.8×10^{16} ions/cm²; 3 μm wide areas) and (b) (3.2×10^{16} - 3.1×10^{17} ions/cm²; 3 μm wide areas). (c, d) 3D view of AFM topographies corresponding to data in panels (a) and (b). (e) 2D AFM map of data from panel (a); a section profile of the upper second row of FIB-treated areas is superimposed on the topography map. (f) Depth of the FIB-treated areas as measured with AFM relative to topographic data of panels (a) (in red) and (b) (in black).

3.2 Structural analysis - RAMAN spectra of FIB milled areas

Raman spectroscopy has been widely used to assess FIB-induced structural damage in III-V semiconductors and heterostructures, as well as in thin oxide films [28-31]. In general, ion irradiation produces broadening, shifts, and intensity changes of the Raman-active vibrational bands, reflecting disorder, amorphization, implantation damage, strain, and changes in local bonding. These spectral modifications provide a convenient

way to estimate the FIB milling induced evolution of the structural and chemical properties in the InGaAs, InP, and HfO₂ materials object of this work.

The Raman spectra of the two samples in the regions not treated with FIB are reported in Fig. 3, together with the reference spectrum of InP material acquired on the bare InP substrate. The Raman spectrum of InP shows the characteristic InP-LO (307 cm⁻¹), InP-TO (346 cm⁻¹) peaks.

Noticeably, the spectra of the two samples with and without HfO₂ film show similar features. Peaks due to the InAs-like LO and GaAs-like LO modes are clearly present, positioned at approximately 228 cm⁻¹ and 267 cm⁻¹, respectively, which are typical of the ternary InGaAs alloy. The two contributions are not sharply distinct, owing to the overlap with intermediate features associated with various mechanisms, including high doping, strain and possible local disorder [32]. The small differences in relative intensity of the InGaAs related peaks are likely due to the HfO₂ film deposition process and/or interface states in the capped sample.

In the high-wavenumber spectral region (700-1500 cm⁻¹, see inset of Fig. 3), broad bands are present, at around 1300 cm⁻¹, with different intensity for the two samples, commonly attributed to carbon contamination. No other relevant structures ascribable to the studied material or to the HfO₂ film are visible, indicating good optical transparency of the capping oxide film at the laser wavelength used. However, the spectrum acquired on the capped sample shows an increased level of noise in the signal, probably caused by a slightly reduced accuracy of laser focusing on the underlying material.

FIGURE 3. Raman spectra acquired on the untreated regions of the two samples, InGaAs (150 nm)/InP (black curve) and HfO₂ (35 nm)/InGaAs (150 nm)/InP (red curve), and on the InP bare substrate (blue curve). The inset shows a detailed view of the spectral range 700–1500 cm⁻¹.

The Raman spectra collected on the regions treated with FIB at increasing doses on the two samples are shown in Fig. 4.

FIGURE 4. Raman spectra collected in the FIB treated regions on the two investigated samples: (a) InGaAs (150 nm)/InP and (b) HfO₂(35 nm)/InGaAs(150 nm)/InP. The curves marked with an asterisk in the two panels exhibit an almost identical shape and a similar intensity ratio between the InAs-like and GaAs-like peaks. Bottom (red) curves are the spectra corresponding to the respective untreated areas. Top (black) curves show the reference spectrum for InP collected on the bare InP substrate. Vertical grey lines are visual guides corresponding to the main Raman peak positions.

3.2.1 Raman spectra of InGaAs/InP sample

The Raman spectra of the 150 nm heavily doped InGaAs layer grown on an InP substrate show a clear evolution as a function of FIB dose. Three distinct regimes can be identified: low, intermediate, and high milling doses. In the low-dose range ($\sim 2 \times 10^{14} - 5 \times 10^{15}$ ions/cm²), corresponding to a FIB milling depth of up to approximately 15 nm, the most noticeable feature is an abrupt change in the relative intensity of the GaAs-like and InAs-like contributions, with respect to the spectrum of the untreated sample, already at the lowest investigated dose (1.96×10^{14} ions/cm²). At this very low dose, the milling depth is barely measurable, while most of the incident Ga⁺ ions are expected to be implanted near the surface, leading to the formation of Ga-As-related complexes (that is to an inversion in the InAs-like/GaAs-like peak intensity ratio) and to broadening of InAs-like and GaAs-like Raman bands. As the dose increases, this broadening becomes more pronounced and is accompanied by a progressive reduction in the InAs-like component, consistent with a gradual increase in the local Ga/In ratio within the irradiated regions. In this initial stage, ion implantation dominates over sputtering, causing a modification of the effective composition and a relative enhancement of the GaAs-like contribution with respect to the InAs-like one. The persistence of a stronger GaAs-like peak over the entire investigated dose range indicates a continuous depletion of indium relative to gallium in the semiconductor. The broadening and attenuation of the InGaAs-related band intensity can be attributed to ion-bombardment-induced defects and progressive amorphization of the material. Under these conditions, the milling process evolves from an initially shallow damage regime toward a steady-state condition, in which the shallow defected layer in the InGaAs film is expected to be ~ 40 nm thick, as reported in previous studies [10].

In the intermediate dose range ($\sim 5 \times 10^{15} - 4 \times 10^{16}$ ions/cm²), corresponding to a milling depth between ~ 15 nm and 150 nm, the InAs-like component progressively decreases and develops a strongly asymmetric, almost triangular profile, with a more pronounced tail toward lower wavenumbers. In this regime, weak intermediate features between the two main InAs-like and GaAs-like Raman peaks become visible, particularly in the dose range corresponding to a removed InGaAs depth of approximately 30 nm to 50 nm ($\sim 1.5 \times 10^{16}$ ions/cm²).

At the highest dose range ($4 \times 10^{16} - 6 \times 10^{16}$ ions/cm²), corresponding to a removed material thickness of approximately 150-300 nm, a weak but distinct peak centered at about 347cm^{-1} appears, and starts increasing in intensity. This feature can be attributed to the LO Raman mode of InP, indicating that the residual InGaAs layer has become sufficiently thin to allow the probe to sense the underlying substrate. In the same spectral region, a large band arises, progressively broadens and slightly shifts towards lower wavenumbers with increasing dose, consistent with the accumulation of implantation-induced defects in the crystalline InP and with the development of a steady-state damaged layer, expected to extend to about 60 nm under FIB conditions [10].

3.2.2 Raman spectra of HfO₂/InGaAs/InP sample

The Raman spectra of the HfO₂/InGaAs/InP sample show an evolution qualitatively similar to that observed for the InGaAs/InP sample, with some specific differences associated with the presence of the HfO₂ top layer. The investigated ion-dose range is broader, spanning approximately $5.6 \times 10^{12} - 3.1 \times 10^{17}$ ions/cm², in order to include both a low-dose regime in which the FIB effects are largely confined within the 35-nm-thick HfO₂ film, and a high-dose regime in which the InGaAs layer is completely removed, exposing the underlying InP substrate. With respect to untreated regions, the FIB irradiation induces a more gradual evolution in the intensity ratio between the InAs-like and GaAs-like peaks, which changes from an InAs-like-dominated to a GaAs-like-dominated type. At doses around 5×10^{14} ions/cm², corresponding to a reduction of the HfO₂ thickness by less than 2 nm, the InGaAs-related band begins to broaden symmetrically on both sides, in contrast with the uncapped InGaAs/InP sample. This behavior suggests that some Ga ions penetrate through the HfO₂ layer and reach the underlying InGaAs film, producing a moderate degree of defectivity. Around a dose of 7×10^{15} ions/cm², the Raman features of the InGaAs related band resembles that of the InGaAs/InP sample irradiated at a dose of about 2×10^{14} ions/cm² (see the two corresponding curves marked with an asterisk in Fig. 4a and b). This comparison suggests that HfO₂ initially acts as a buffer layer, retaining most of the incident Ga ions within the oxide until significant amorphization of the cap allows the ions to reach the semiconductor material below. For doses above approximately 7×10^{15} ions/cm², the two main Raman contributions remain comparable in intensity, although the overall InGaAs-related band gradually decreases until the HfO₂ layer is almost completely removed, which happens at a dose of about 8×10^{16} ions/cm² corresponding to a FIB-milled depth of approximately 35 nm. As the dose increases further, the InGaAs band broadens and increases in intensity. When the residual InGaAs thickness approaches 35-40 nm, a Raman feature associated with InP becomes visible near 340cm^{-1} ; this feature then evolves into two well-defined and intense peaks, typical of crystalline InP, once the InGaAs layer is fully removed at doses around 1.9×10^{17} ions/cm², when InGaAs Raman bands disappear.

Overall, the Raman analysis shows a more pronounced progressive broadening of the InGaAs band, accompanied by a gradual loss of the InAs-like component, for the sample without the HfO₂ top layer. This result is consistent with a protective or “ion-filtering” effect of the dielectric layer in the HfO₂/InGaAs/InP sample. For both samples, once material removal reaches the InP substrate, the Raman spectra show large defect bands with superimposed features related to crystalline materials, more evident in the HfO₂ capped sample.

3.3 Local impedance analysis - SMM mapping of FIB milled areas

As mentioned, in addition to morphological and structural modifications, focused ion beam treatment is expected to induce changes in the electrical and dielectric properties of the material over a shallow depth, typically extending to several tens of nanometers.

SMM probes the response of materials under microwave excitation through the S11 coefficient, thereby providing information about local electrical properties even in non-conductive systems coefficient. The S11 parameter is the ratio between the microwave power delivered to the tip and the power reflected back from the tip-sample interface, and it reflects the local complex tip-sample impedance. Moreover, SMM probes a significantly larger interaction volume, enabling subsurface investigation with a probing depth on the order of 100 nm depending on the material under study, substantially exceeding that of conventional conductive AFM, which is mainly sensitive to tip-sample contact resistance. It is therefore a method of choice for providing complementary information on subsurface electrical variations in FIB milled areas. S11 data collected by SMM on the FIB-treated regions of InGaAs/InP and HfO₂/InGaAs/InP samples are reported in Figs. 5-8. For almost all the ion doses used, the S11 maps (amplitude and phase) show a clear contrast between the FIB-treated areas and the outer regions.

The S11 data for the InGaAs/InP sample are reported in Figs. 5 and 6. Fig. 5a,b show the two-dimensional S11 amplitude and phase maps, in which the FIB-treated areas exhibit evident false colour contrast with respect to the surrounding untreated regions, even at the lowest investigated dose of 1.96×10^{14} ion/cm². As the FIB milling dose increases, the S11 amplitude data in the coloured map (Fig. 5a) follows a monotonic decrease (from yellow to dark colour). Oppositely, the phase signal map shows an increase in its value, visible as a transition from blue to dark rose colour in the square FIB treated areas. Cross-sectional profiles of the maps corresponding to the five highest doses used are reported in Fig. 5c,d, showing the S11 amplitude and phase behaviour in the ion-irradiated square areas with respect to the outside untreated regions. At the edges of the treated areas, both signals exhibit peak-like features, which may be associated with different implantation conditions near the borders and/or artifacts due to morphological interactions of the edges of the milled structures with the SMM probe which can reflect in the S11 response. For this reason, the S11 data as a function of FIB-milled depth were obtained by averaging the values within the very central region of each FIB treated square area. These S11 amplitude and phase data vs. FIB-milled depth as measured with AFM, are reported in Fig. 6. Starting from low ion doses, the amplitude and phase data remain almost constant up to a milling depth in the InGaAs film of about 10 nm. For higher ion doses, a monotonic behavior is visible, decreasing for the amplitude and increasing for the phase, as described and pictorially discernible in the 2D maps. Two distinct regimes with different slopes can be identified in the 10-300nm milling depth range of the semilogarithmic plots: i) a first one up to the complete removal of the InGaAs film (10 to 150 nm) and ii) a final region (150 to 300 nm), where FIB milling proceeds within the InP layer and the slope of the curves becomes steeper.

At low ion doses, the S11 amplitude and phase remain nearly constant and are shifted with respect to the values measured in the external untreated areas (indicated by the dashed horizontal lines in Fig. 6). A reasonable interpretation is that, at these low doses, the treated regions undergo Ga implantation, which induces damage in the form of amorphization of a shallow InGaAs layer which modifies its electrical properties. While a small fraction of the film thickness is affected by implantation, the SMM interaction volume still includes a large portion of the underlying undamaged crystalline InGaAs, explaining the nearly flat behaviour. This finding is consistent with the Raman data in Fig. 4, where the spectra recorded up to a milling depth of ~10 nm are very similar to each other, but clearly different from the reference spectrum of the untreated areas, showing a significant broadening of the InGaAs Raman band. At milling depth values larger than ~10 nm, the FIB process is expected to have reached a steady-state milling and damage regime that is known to produce an amorphous layer of approximately 40 nm [10], which becomes increasingly comparable to the remaining crystalline InGaAs thickness. In parallel, the Raman spectra show a change in the relative intensity of the InAs-like and GaAs-like bands, suggesting a modification of the In/Ga composition of the semiconductor, which further affects the electrical properties detected by SMM as a slope in the amplitude and phase data (blue line in Fig. 4), i.e., a logarithmic variation of the S11 signal. A relevant change in slope occurs at a milling depth of around 150 nm, corresponding to the initial thickness of the InGaAs film. This finding is consistent with the change in electrical properties associated with the transition from InGaAs to InP as the more relevant semiconductor probed by SMM. The linear behavior in the semilogarithmic plot is similar to that observed for the InGaAs layer, indicating a progressive material damage consistent with the defect band with increasing intensity visible at high doses in the Raman signal of InP.

FIGURE 5. SMM data collected on the InGaAs/InP sample. SMM map of (a) amplitude and (b) phase of S_{11} . Section profiles of (c) the amplitude and (d) phase of S_{11} along the dashed line shown in (a) and (b), respectively.

FIGURE 6. (a) Amplitude and (b) phase of S_{11} signal for the InGaAs/InP sample upon increasing the FIB treatment ion dose. The vertical line represents the interface between InGaAs and InP layers. The horizontal line indicates the amplitude and phase levels in the respective untreated areas.

On the other hand, for the $\text{HfO}_2/\text{InGaAs}/\text{InP}$ sample, the presence of the three-layer stack and the different FIB milling rates of the three materials generate a more complex scenario compared to the sample consisting of InGaAs/InP.

The S_{11} data for the $\text{HfO}_2/\text{InGaAs}/\text{InP}$ sample are reported in Figs. 7 and 8. Fig. 7(a,b) show the two-dimensional data maps of the S_{11} amplitude and phase, respectively, where a clear contrast between the FIB-treated areas and the surrounding untreated regions is already visible even at the lowest ion doses in the investigated

range, $1.96 \times 10^{14} - 6.08 \times 10^{16}$ ions/cm². As the FIB milling dose increases, both the S11 amplitude and phase exhibit a similar qualitative evolution, with an initial monotonic increase variation followed by a pronounced maximum at a dose of about $2 \times 10^{16} - 3 \times 10^{16}$ ions/cm², corresponding to a milled depth of approximately 10–15 nm, and then a subsequent decrease. To extend the analysis to both lower and higher doses, additional FIB-patterned arrays were fabricated, and the corresponding amplitude and phase data are reported in Fig. 8 for two patterns treated under different dose ranges. Although the measurements were acquired at different times and with different SMM probes, the overall qualitative trends remain consistent, despite the quantitative discrepancies between the curves (note that each curve has its own Y-axis), which supports the robustness of the technique on the investigated material system. At the lowest doses (up to $\sim 4 \times 10^{16}$ ions/cm²), the milled depth remains smaller than the thickness of the HfO₂ capping layer, and the observed modulation of the SMM signal is primarily associated with ion implantation in the oxide. In this regime, the S11 response reflects progressive changes in the electrical properties of HfO₂ as a result of Ga incorporation and structural damage, which alter both its effective thickness and dielectric behavior. As confirmed from Raman spectra, that in this dose range show only limited broadening of the InGaAs-related features, the HfO₂ layer still partially protects the underlying InGaAs film from significant damage. A slight change in the relative intensity of the InAs-like and GaAs-like Raman bands suggests that a small amount of Ga ions may already penetrate through the oxide and reach the crystalline InGaAs layer, increasing the local Ga concentration within the semiconductor matrix. At intermediate doses, corresponding to milling depths of $\sim 10-15$ nm, the HfO₂ layer becomes strongly modified and progressively less effective as a protective cap. In this range, the SMM response reaches a maximum and then begins to decrease, indicating that the microwave probe is sensing not only the damaged oxide but also the underlying semiconductor stack. Raman data support this interpretation by showing a more evident broadening of the InGaAs-related spectral features, consistent with implantation-induced disorder and amorphization. Around a dose of about 3×10^{16} ions/cm², the Raman spectrum becomes very similar to that observed for the uncapped InGaAs/InP sample at the lowest investigated dose, suggesting that a comparable level of damage, broadening, and structural modification is eventually reached in the semiconductor beneath the oxide cap. These observations suggest that the HfO₂ layer initially acts as an effective buffer against Ga implantation, but that its protective role progressively weakens as ion-induced damage, thinning, and local morphological inhomogeneity develop. For larger milling depths, around 15-20 nm and beyond, the SMM signals show a sharp decrease toward lower values, consistent with the response expected once the HfO₂ film is completely removed (see data in Fig. 8 for FIB milled depth $> 25-35$ nm). This transition occurs before complete removal of the HfO₂ layer, implying that the microwave response is already influenced by the modified underlying InGaAs film. The abrupt change is therefore consistent with the combined effects of oxide thinning, oxide amorphization, and increasing ion penetration into the conductive semiconductor below. Once the HfO₂ layer is sufficiently thinned, or less effective as a dielectric due to implantation and damage, the electrical response becomes dominated by the semiconductor stack. However, the S11 amplitude and phase follow a different behaviour from that observed in the InGaAs/InP sample. In fact, in the sample with top HfO₂ this transition is less abrupt and less easily separable because the surface morphology becomes increasingly heterogeneous as the FIB dose increases. Indeed, the HfO₂-capped sample exhibits a strong morphological sensitivity to milling dose. The oxide layer is rapidly modified by the ion beam, and small inhomogeneities in the oxide lead to the formation of localized pits (see SEM images and AFM maps of Fig. 2b,d), which are then amplified by the much faster (~ 12 x) milling rate of the underlying semiconductors relative to HfO₂. Consequently, at the highest doses the surface becomes highly rough and locally non-uniform, and the same FIB treated area may contain a mixture of HfO₂, InGaAs, and even InP. This coexistence of multiple materials naturally produces a mixed SMM response, which is harder to interpret than in the bare InGaAs/InP sample. In the latter case, the smoother morphology and the simpler two-layer structure allow the S11 signal to be more directly associated with the progressive transition from one semiconductor to the other, whereas in the HfO₂/InGaAs/InP sample the signal reflects a superposition of dielectric degradation, semiconductor damage, and morphological roughening.

FIGURE 7. SMM data collected on the $\text{HfO}_2/\text{InGaAs}/\text{InP}$ sample in the dose range $1.9\text{E}14 - 6.8\text{E}16$ ions/ cm^2 . SMM maps of (a) amplitude and (b) phase of S_{11} . Section profiles of the (c) amplitude and (d) phase of S_{11} along the dashed lines shown in (a) and (b) respectively.

FIGURE 8. (a) Amplitude and (b) phase of S_{11} signal for the $\text{HfO}_2/\text{InGaAs}/\text{InP}$ sample upon increasing the FIB treatment ion dose. The red and blue curve refer to the FIB patterns reported in the panel (a) and panel (b) of Fig. 2, respectively. Vertical lines and labels in the graphs highlight the interfaces between the $\text{HfO}_2/\text{InGaAs}$ and the InGaAs/InP layers.

4. Conclusions

This work demonstrates that scanning microwave microscopy is a sensitive and non-destructive tool for tracking FIB-induced changes in the local microwave response of III-V heterostructures. In the InGaAs/InP sample, SMM captures the progressive transition from implantation-dominated modification of the InGaAs layer to an InP-dominated response once the semiconductor film is fully removed. In the HfO₂/InGaAs/InP stack, SMM reveals a more complex evolution because the HfO₂ capping layer initially buffers ion damage but then undergoes progressive structural degradation and loss of dielectric properties. At the same time, its protective function diminishes leading to a non-trivial SMM mixed response from the damaged oxide, the underlying InGaAs, and eventually the InP substrate. Combined with AFM and Raman data, the SMM results show that the two heterostructures follow distinct damage pathways and that scanning microwave microscopy can provide complementary information, enabling a more complete identification of nanoscale electrical and dielectric changes induced by FIB milling. These findings support the use of SMM as a powerful diagnostic tool for evaluating FIB processing windows in layered semiconductor systems and for guiding the fabrication of mid-infrared plasmonic nanodevices where nanoscale control of electrical integrity is essential. A more quantitative interpretation would benefit from dedicated calibration structures in proximity to the FIB patterns that allow the conversion of S11 variations into calibrated electrical observables.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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